

Carpological analysis of a Roman well at the site of *Alba Fucens* (Abruzzi, Italy)

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Figure 1. a) and b) geographical position of *Alba Fucens*; c) the archaeological site; d) the well in the sanctuary of Hercules

Introduction

- Few sites investigated in the Abruzzi region
- ***Alba Fucens***: founded in the late 4th century BC and prosperous during the Imperial age

Materials & Methods

- **Roman well** in the Sanctuary of Hercules
 - part of the water conveyance system
 - fill resulting from the destruction of the sanctuary following an earthquake (5th-6th century AD)
 - 6 stratigraphic units processed (12.6 kg)
- Wet sieving → waterlogged materials

Results & Discussion

- > 1500 carpological remains
- **70 taxa** → terrestrial plants and Bryophytes
- Gathered fruit plants and spontaneous species

